

Supporting Information

Apparent colors of 2D materials

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In order to give more information and simplicity to the reader, we offer several figures, in which the optimum thicknesses of the selected substrates are shown by using different materials with dependence of the wavenumber of the light used to calculate optical contrast.

Figure S1. (a) Calculated C color maps for monolayer graphene as a function of the illumination wavelength and SiO_2 thickness. Reprinted from ^[9], with permission from AIP Publishing.

Figure S2. (a) Calculated C color maps for monolayer MoS_2 as a function of the illumination wavelength and SiO_2 thickness. Reprinted from ^[76].

Figure S3. Calculated C of a monolayer of TiS_3 as a function of the illumination wavelength and SiO_2 thickness. Reproduced from ^[261].

Figure S4. Calculated C color maps for monolayer franckeite as a function of the illumination wavelength and SiO_2 thickness. Reproduced from ^[301].

Figure S5. Calculated C color maps for monolayer PbI₂ as a function of the illumination wavelength and SiO₂ thickness. Reprinted from ^[310]. Copyright (2017), with permission from IOP Publishing.